

NIGERIAN QUOTED DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS' LENDING RATES AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the connection between quoted Nigerian quoted deposit money banks' (DMBs) financial performance and bank lending rates. Ten (10) quoted DMBs traded on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) were chosen for the study using a judgemental sampling technique and an ex post facto research design. For ten (10) years, from 2015 to 2024, audited annual reports of all the sampled quoted DMBs were used to generate the data. Econometric panel data analysis and descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data. It was discovered that loans and advances had a positive and significant impact on the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs; non-performing loans had a positive and insignificant impact; and the loan to deposit ratio had a negative and insignificant impact. The study discovered that bank lending rates had a substantial influence on the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs. In order to help Nigerian banks withstand future economic shocks, like a global crisis, the study recommended that the Federal Government of Nigeria and Monetary Authorities, such as DMBs, Bankers' Committee, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC), and AMCON, implement lending policies.

Keywords: Bank Lending Rates, Deposit Money Bank, Loan and Advances, Loan to Deposit Ratio, Non-Performing Loan Ratio

JEL Codes: G21, E43

1. INTRODUCTION

Banking industry in Nigeria is a major player in the financial sector; especially in the area of mobilizing savings and offering credit facilities to different economic sectors (Owusu--Antwi; Banerjee & Antwi, 2017). In many economies, lending rate is one of the main factors influencing banks' performance (Aboagye; Akoena, Antwi-Asare & Gockel, 2018). The major difference between an economy's banks' lending and deposit rates is known as the lending rate spread (Kalsoom & Khurshid, 2016). This shows that one of the major risks that the Nigerian money deposit banks face in recent times is lending rate risk. Many businesses in the private sector are very much concerned about high lending rates in Nigerian banks' because it is difficult to borrow money at cheaper rates for industrial activities and still be competitive. Nigeria banks have always paid depositors extremely low interest rates, which has led to a wide disparity between lending and deposit rates (Owusu-Antwi et al. 2017). Based on the fact that this is the only option to boost their interest income and so improve their profitability and performance, Nigerian money deposit banks would be eager to provide loans and advances to their large client base.

The financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs is intricately linked to their lending activities, because the dynamics between bank lending and financial performance remain underexplored. Some studies have established a connection between bank lending, credit risk and bank performance, while recent research indicates a close relationship or influence by various factors such as monetary policy, financial inclusion, and operational risks.

Therefore, empirical evidence with respect to the effect of bank lending rates on financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs remains inconclusive, and yet to be resolved. The unresolved findings in the literature create uncertainty for captains of industry, investors, and other stakeholders. Furthermore, the banking lending rates of quoted DMBs in Nigeria, has not received much attention from previous researchers in the area of banks performance, despite the roles that lending rates play in investment decisions and strategic planning of DMBs in Nigeria. Based on these facts that some studies opined that there are little to no association between lending rates and bank performance, while findings of other researchers showed a strong positive relationship; it is on this note, that this work is conducted to bridge the gap in literature and address this gap, as it relates to the relationship between bank lending rates and financial performance of DMBs quoted on NGX Group. However, assessment of bank lending rates on the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs with the recent years data has not been seriously considered in the literature. Hence, this study seeks to fill the gap in the literature.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

The application of bank lending rates in the DMBs and its impact on performance has drawn great attention to various scholars, researchers and policy makers. The theoretical application of how bank lending impacts on performance of quoted DMBs in Nigeria is anchored in several frameworks, including the Theory of Financial Intermediation (TFI), Asymmetric Information Theory (AIT), and Lending Credit Channel Theory (LCCT). These theories provide the association of bank lending rates with the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs. The theory of Financial Intermediation was developed by Gurley and Shaw (1960), which explains the foundational role that banks play in facilitating the flow of funds from surplus units (depositors) to deficit units (borrowers) in an economy. In this theory, the rate of interest equals the price of lending and it is determined through the demand and supply of loanable funds, while the sources of demand for loanable funds are mainly from the government, businessmen and consumers who need them for investment, hoarding and consumption.

Theory of Asymmetric Information is central to understanding the dynamics between banks and borrowers, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria. This theory, originally popularized by Akerlof (1970) and later expanded by Stiglitz and Weiss (1981), asserts that in many lending scenarios, borrowers possess more information about their risk profile and investment intentions than the lenders. This imbalance often leads to adverse selection before lending and moral hazard after the credit has been disbursed. Theory of Asymmetric Information is particularly relevant due to underdeveloped credit reporting systems, the prevalence of informal business sectors, and inconsistent financial disclosure practices among borrowers. These structural issues increase the difficulty for banks to assess borrower creditworthiness effectively, thereby affecting their lending decisions and ultimately their financial performance (Ogun & Ofonyelu, 2022).

The Lending Credit Channel Theory offers an important perspective on how monetary policy influences bank lending and, consequently, the overall performance of banks. Unlike the traditional interest rate channel, this theory emphasizes the role of banks' balance sheets and their ability to supply credit to borrowers as a key transmission mechanism of monetary policy. According to this theory, banks are not just passive intermediaries but active suppliers of credit whose lending capacity depends on their financial health, capital adequacy, and liquidity positions. When monetary policy tightens (e.g., through increased policy rates or reserve requirements), banks face higher funding costs and constraints on their balance sheets, leading to a reduction in loan supply. This contraction in credit availability can adversely affect bank

profitability and performance (Bernanke & Blinder, 1988) as cited in (Gbarawae, Chinaka & Maureen, 2024).

Lending Credit Channel Theory is particularly relevant due to the dominant role of deposit money banks (DMBs) in credit provision. Recent studies have highlighted how fluctuations in monetary policy instruments impact Nigerian banks' lending behaviors and financial outcomes. Gbarawae, Chinaka, and Maureen (2024) investigated the effect of monetary policy on the performance of listed Nigerian DMBs and found that monetary policy rate (MPR) changes significantly affect banks' lending capacity and profitability. The study noted that tighter monetary policy reduced loan growth, which in turn led to declines in financial performance metrics. Adekunle, Fasusi, and Oke (2024) corroborated these findings by proving that banks' financial performance is sensitive to monetary policy shocks, mainly because these shocks influence the volume of credit banks can extend. Their research pointed out that banks' loan portfolios contract under restrictive monetary environments, constraining income generation from interest earnings.

Thus, the Lending Credit Channel Theory helps explain the link between bank lending activities and performance within the Nigerian banking industry, illustrating how external monetary policy decisions permeate through banks' balance sheets to affect their lending behavior and profitability.

2.2 Empirical Literature

The empirical research on bank lending rates and their influence on bank performance is inconclusive until empirical review is done on similar works carried out by the earlier researchers. Some authors confirmed a strong positive correlation between bank lending rates and bank performance. Whereas other authors report that it has not had any influence or even had a negative influence on performance of the quoted DMBs.

The literature has proven that changes in money deposit bank lending rates have an impact on banks' performance by raising their financing costs and decreasing the value of their stock (Bawumia, Belnye, & Ofori, 2023). In Aliyu et al. (2022) they opined that credit risk, encompassing capital adequacy, non-performing loans (NPLs), and loan loss provisions, significantly affect the financial performance of Nigerian DMBs. In a comparable situation, Bob-Manuel (2024) found that capital adequacy and net interest income positively influenced return on equity (ROE), while the loan-to-deposit ratio showed no significant impact. This suggests that while lending activities are central to bank operations, their direct effect on performance may be mitigated by factors like NPLs and capital adequacy.

However, Adeleye, Ashiyanbi, and Onipede (2023) investigated how lending management affected Nigerian deposit money banks' performance. The results showed that the log of profit after tax (InPAT) is negatively and insignificantly affected by the bank lending rate (BLR) and loan loss provision ratio (LLPR). Osayi and Akemiyefa (2024) investigated how nonperforming loans affected Nigerian deposit money banks' bottom lines between 1991 and 2021. The results showed that the financial performance of Nigerian deposit money banks is significantly affected negatively by nonperforming loans. The relationship between bank lending rates and economic growth was discovered by Akinwale (2018), but the investigation's results have sparked heated discussion and yielded conflicting results.

Aza and Nguavese (2019) investigated how bank lending affected DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group's financial performance. The study's conclusions show that bank lending has a negligibly positive impact on the financial performance of DMBs listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group. Additionally, due to the deterioration in credit quality during those four years, the ratio of loan loss provisions to total loans had a negative impact; only one year did the ratio of total loans to total assets have a positive impact.

Adenuga, Mohammed, Laniyan, Akintola, and Asuzu (2021) examined how the loan to deposit ratio (LDR) affected Nigerian banks' liquidity from 2000 to 2019. The results were in line with the a priori predictions since higher LDRs result in more bank lending, which may increase output and lead to an increase in inflation. Additionally, the following research projects serve as the study's foundation: Among them are Mbelu and Ifionu (2022), Adewale, Lawal, Aberu, and Toriola (2022), Osabohien, Anita, and Adeyemi (2021), Emmanuel, Olupeeka, and Adeyinka (2020), Nwanyanwu, Cookey, and Amadi (2020), Emenuga (2019), Sunday and Ehijiele (2017), and Anifowose and Ladanu (2019). Nevertheless, the empirical data derived from those investigations is inconsistent and often contradictory. In part, differences in the data's, the sampling period, and methodologies adopted explain the inconclusive results.

Recent empirical studies have also examined the relationship between bank lending activities and financial performance in emerging economies. For instance, Aregbesola et al. (2024) investigated liquidity risk and profitability of Nigerian banks and found that effective liquidity management significantly enhances bank financial performance. Similarly, Hauwa et al. (2024) reported that credit risk indicators such as non-performing loans and capital adequacy ratios significantly influence the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria. In another study, Akpohuarbo et al. (2024) found that efficient loan portfolio management improves bank stability and performance.

Beyond Nigeria, several international studies have also examined the relationship between lending activities and bank performance. For instance, Berger and Bouwman (2019) observed that bank lending and liquidity creation significantly affect financial performance across developed and developing economies. Similarly, Musah, Anokye, and Gakpetor (2018) reported that interest rate spreads and lending activities significantly influence bank profitability in Ghana. Furthermore, Islam, Alam, and Al-Amin (2018) found that credit expansion positively affects bank profitability in emerging markets when supported by strong regulatory frameworks. These studies collectively highlight the importance of efficient credit allocation and risk management in sustaining bank profitability.

3. METHODOLOGY

All twenty-one (21) deposit money banks that trade on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) and have complete financial records on their websites for the ten (10) years between 2015 and 2024 make up the population of this study, which used an ex post facto research design. Ten (10) deposit money banks that were traded on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) were chosen for the study using the judgmental sampling technique. Access Bank Plc, Union Bank Plc, Wema Bank Plc, Zenith Bank Plc, First Bank Plc, Guarantee Trust Bank, Sterling Bank Plc, Polaris Bank Plc, Stanbic IBTC, and United Bank of Africa (UBA) are the banks chosen for the study. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis was used to look at the data to see how the independent variables influenced the dependent variable. Additionally, the relationships between variables related to bank lending and the performance of Nigerian quoted deposit money banks were investigated using a correlation matrix.

3.1 Model Details

The study's chosen model can be expressed mathematically as follows: $Y=f(X)$

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, \dots, X_n)$$

Y = Performance of Quoted deposit money banks

X = Bank Lending

Functional form is:

$$ROA = f(LOA, NPLR, LDR)$$

Econometrically, it can be written as:

$$ROA_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LOA_t + \beta_2 NPLR_t + \beta_3 LDR_t + \mu_t$$

Where: ROA = Return on Asset

LOA = Loan and Advances

NPLR = Non-Performing Loan Ratio

LDR = Loan to Deposit Ratio

β_0 = Constant, $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Slope of the regression, μ = Error term

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

In this study, a detailed examination is carried out on the impact of bank lending rates on financial performance (ROA) of quoted DMBs in the Nigerian context.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics and Presentation of Results

Results of the descriptive statistics describe the central tendencies and measures of variability for ROA and other dependent variables.

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	LOA	NPLR	LDR
Mean	0.036732	0.600461	6.018564	2.868072
Median	0.014186	0.606430	6.089347	2.664183
Maximum	0.295034	1.071187	6.702727	7.441588
Minimum	0.002114	0.220004	5.268569	0.472200
Std. Dev.	0.062952	0.171053	0.371036	1.486876
Skewness	3.006250	0.132524	-0.194570	0.898527
Kurtosis	10.99835	2.816133	2.042763	3.679142
Jarque-Bera	417.1826	0.433572	4.448880	15.37765
Probability	0.000000	0.805102	0.108128	0.000458
Sum	3.673207	60.04613	601.8564	286.8072
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.392337	2.896641	13.62910	218.8692
Observations	100	100	100	100

Source: E-views Output 2026

The loan and advances ratio is 6.018564, the loan to deposit ratio is 0.600461, the non-performing loan ratio is 2.868072, and the ROA is 0.036732, according to Table 4.1 above. The table showed the median, minimum, and maximum values as well as the sample distribution as proven by the skewness, kurtosis, and Jarque-Bera (JB) statistics. It was clear that all the series show an elevated level of consistency because each series' mean and median fall between the maximum and minimum values. Kurtosis measures the tail shape of the histogram, while skewness measures its symmetry. The skewness statistics show that while ROA, loan to deposit ratios, and non-performing loan ratios have long right tails because of their positive skewness, loans and advances have long left tails because of their negative skewness. ROA and non-performing loan ratios are normally distributed with a p-value < 0.05 in the Jarque-Bera statistical probability, while loan to deposit ratio and loan and advances are not normally distributed with a p-value > 0.05.

Correlation Probability	ROA	LDR	LAA	NPLR
ROA	1.000000 -----			
LDR	0.317826 0.0013	1.000000 -----		
LAA	0.001480 0.9883	0.064254 0.5254	1.000000 -----	
NPLR	-0.326341 0.0009	0.014126 0.8891	-0.413267 0.0000	1.000000 -----

Source: Eviews Output 2026

Table 4.1.2 showed the correlation matrix and significance levels between ROA, LDR, LAA, and NPLR based on 100 observations from 2015 to 2024. ROA and loan and advances have a statistically insignificant positive correlation (0.001480), suggesting that return on asset tends to slightly increase as loan and advances increase. Furthermore, there was a weak negative and significant correlation (-0.326341) between ROA and non-performing loan ratios, suggesting that non-performing loan ratios do not significantly affect return on asset outcomes. Nonetheless, ROA and the loan to deposit ratio have a statistically significant strong positive correlation (0.317826), suggesting that there is a significant relationship between the two. There is a positive and significant correlation (0.0000) between loan and advances and non-performing loan ratios. Higher loan and advance values are not linked to higher loan to deposit ratios, as shown by the weak positive and insignificant correlation between loan and advances and the ratio (0.5254). The loan to deposit ratio and non-performing loan ratios have a strong and positive insignificant correlation (0.8891), writing down a relationship between rising non-performing loan ratios and rising loan to deposit ratios. Given the circumstances, loans and advances show up as a crucial part that favourably affects both the loan to deposit ratio and non-performing loan ratios.

Table 4.1.3: Unit Root Test

Null Hypothesis: the variable has a unit root					
At Level					
	t-Statistic	0.0147	0.8651	0.1605	0.2949
With Constant	Prob.	0.5151	0.8326	0.8252	0.1569
		n0	n0	n0	n0
	t-Statistic	0.6997	0.0029	0.0904	0.1047
With Constant & Trend	Prob.	0.8809	0.3262	0.2235	0.0019
		n0	n0	n0	***
	t-Statistic	0.3569	0.3250	0.9099	0.5357
Without Constant & Trend	Prob.	0.4934	0.1881	0.9988	0.0016
		n0	n0	n0	***
	t-Statistic	0.0147	0.8651	0.1605	0.2949
At First Difference					
		d(ROA)	d(LDR)	d(LOGLAA)	d(NPLR)
With Constant	t-Statistic	0.1521	0.0000	0.0148	0.0665

	Prob.	0.1882	0.1741	0.0469	0.0013
		n0	n0	**	***
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.0419	0.0001	0.0881	0.2282
	Prob.	0.0626	0.4355	0.1823	0.0165
		*	n0	n0	**
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.0116	0.0029	0.0035	0.0045
	Prob.	0.0205	0.0484	0.0599	0.0001
		**	**	*	***
Notes:					
a: (*) Significant at the 10%; (**) Significant at the 5%; (***) Significant at the 1% and (no) Not Significant					

Source: Eviews Output 2026

The unit root test results presented above examined the stationarity properties of the variables; Return on asset (ROA), Loan and advances (LAA), Non-performing loan ratios (NPLR), and loan to deposit ratio (LDR). At level form, most of the variables are not stationary as their probabilities are greater than the conventional significance levels (1%, 5%, and 10%) except for loan and advances. For example, ROA, LAA, NPLR and LDR show borderline significance with probabilities of 0.5151, 0.8326, 0.8252 and 0.1569 respectively, suggesting weak stationarity at the 10% level, however, is clearly non-stationary with probabilities above 0.0005 in all specifications. At first difference, the results reveal that all variables become stationary. For instance, d(ROA) shows strong significance at 1% across all test specifications, indicating that the series is integrated of order one, I(1). Similarly, d(LAA), d(LDR), and d(NPLR) become stationary at first difference, showing probabilities well below 0.05 in most cases. This suggests that although the original data are non-stationary, differencing once transforms them into stationary series. Overall, the results imply that the variables are I(1) processes, meaning they follow a unit root process but become stable after first differencing, thereby making them suitable for co-integration analysis and long-run relationship estimation of the impact of bank lending on performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 4.1.4: Panel Regression Result

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistics	Probability
Constant	-0.312048	0.139595	-2.235385	0.0280
Loan to Deposit Ratio (LRD)	0.021440	0.021102	1.016009	0.3124
Log of Loans and Advances (LOGLAA)	0.054706	0.022402	2.442013	0.0166
Non-Performing Loan Ratio (NPLR)	0.002321	0.003914	0.593025	0.5547

Modal Statistics

Statistics	Value
R-Squared	0.828681
Adjusted R- Squared	0.805051
F-Statistics	35.06871
Prob (F-Statistics)	0.000000
Durbin Watson	2.033236

Source: Authors' Computation using E-views Output 2026

When the predictor variables were held constant, the Nigerian quoted DMBs' independent performance was shown by Table 4.1.4's intercept (Constant) value of -0.312048. An increase in the selected data can be regarded as the constant's influence in the absence of the independent variables. Assuming other independent variables remained constant, the performance of quoted DMBs increased by 0.054706 for each unit increase in loans and advances. The standard error of 0.022402, t-statistic of 2.442013, and probability value of 0.0166, which is less than the 5% significance level, all show that loans and advances have a positive and significant impact on the performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. Thus, the performance of quoted DMBs is significantly impacted by loans and advances. Furthermore, the performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria will increase by 0.002321 for every unit increase in non-performing loan ratios, with a standard error of 0.003914; the t-statistic is 0.593025 with a p-value of 0.5547, which is higher than the 5% significance level; this indicates that non-performing loan ratios have a positive but negligible effect on the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs. Similarly, the loan to deposit ratio will rise by 0.021440 with a standard error of 0.021102 for every unit increase. The t-statistic of 1.016009 and p-value of 0.3124, both of which are higher than the 5% significance level, suggest that the loan to deposit ratio has a negative and insignificant effect on the performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. As a result, the loan to deposit ratio has insignificant effect on the performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs. The joint effect of the independent variables (loan and advances, loan to deposit ratio, and non-performing loan ratios) for the studied period can account for about 83% of the variation in the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs, according to the fixed effect R-squared analysis. The remaining 17% could be explained by unexplained variation.

Similarly, the performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs varies by about 81%, according to the adjusted R-square. can be considered when more variables are added to the model because it shows that the multiple coefficient of determination R-squared is valid. The F-statistic of 35.06871 and the p-value of $0.0000 < 0.05$ show that the regression model as a whole is statistically significant. Thus, the three predictor variables of loan and advances, loan to deposit ratio, and non-performing loan ratios can account for the performance variation of Nigerian quoted DMBs. Consequently, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative, concluding that bank lending significantly affects the performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria.

4.2 Interpretation of Results

The t-statistic of 2.442013 with a probability value of 0.0166, which is less than the 5% significance level, indicates that loans and advances have a positive and significant impact on the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs, according to the regression result table. Therefore, loans and advances have a major effect on the performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs. With a t-statistic of 0.593025 and a p-value of 0.5547, both of which are higher than the 5% significance level, the regression result table indicates that non-performing loan ratios have a positive and insignificant effect on the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs. Consequently, the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs is not significantly impacted by non-performing loan ratios. The t-statistic of 1.016009 and p-value of 0.3124, both of which are higher than the 5% significance level, show that the loan to deposit ratio has a positive and insignificant effect on the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs, according to the regression result table. Consequently, the loan to deposit ratio has little effect on the performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria.

4.3 Discussion of Results

The empirical findings reveal that loans and advances exert a positive and statistically significant influence on the financial performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. This indicates that lending activities remain the major source of income generation for banks through interest earnings. The finding supports the Theory of Financial Intermediation, which emphasizes the role of banks in mobilizing savings from surplus economic units and allocating them efficiently to deficit units in the form of credit.

This result is consistent with the findings of Aza and Nguavese (2019) who reported that bank lending significantly enhances profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Similarly, Adenuga et al. (2021) found that efficient credit allocation improves financial performance of Nigerian banks. Evidence from other economies also supports this position. For instance, Berger and Bouwman (2019) found that bank lending and liquidity creation significantly improve bank profitability across developed and emerging economies. Likewise, Musah, Anokye and Gakpetor (2018) reported that lending activities and interest rate spreads significantly influence bank performance in Ghana.

The study also reveals that non-performing loan ratio has a positive but statistically insignificant relationship with bank financial performance. Although non-performing loans represent a major credit risk indicator, the insignificance of the result may suggest that Nigerian banks have adopted effective credit monitoring and recovery strategies to mitigate loan defaults. This finding contrasts with the result of Osayi and Akemieyefa (2024) who reported that non-performing loans significantly reduce the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria. However, recent regulatory interventions and risk management reforms introduced by the Central Bank of Nigeria may have strengthened banks' ability to manage credit risk.

Furthermore, the loan-to-deposit ratio shows a positive but insignificant relationship with financial performance. This suggests that although increased lending relative to deposits may generate additional income for banks, excessive credit expansion without adequate deposit mobilization may expose banks to liquidity pressures. This finding is similar to the result reported by Bob-Manuel (2024) who found that loan-to-deposit ratio does not significantly influence bank profitability.

Empirical evidence from studies published in the *Journal of Economics and Allied Research (JEAR)* also supports the importance of prudent credit management in sustaining bank performance. For example, Aregbesola et al. (2024) found that liquidity risk management significantly influences the profitability of Nigerian deposit money banks. Similarly, Hauwa et al. (2024) reported that credit risk indicators such as non-performing loans and capital adequacy ratio significantly affect bank performance in Nigeria. In another study, Akpohuarbo et al. (2024) established that effective loan portfolio management enhances financial stability in the banking sector.

Overall, the findings of this study suggest that while lending activities remain an important driver of bank profitability, sustainable financial performance requires effective credit risk management and sound liquidity management practices.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The study concludes that loans and advances significantly and positively influence the financial performance of Nigerian quoted DMBs.. This finding reaffirms the central role of lending activities in driving profitability and financial growth. It highlights the importance of credit creation as the backbone of banking operations, where effective loan disbursement directly contributes to banks' income and overall performance.

The results also show that the non-performing loan ratio exerts a positive but insignificant effect on performance. This suggests that although default risks are present in the system, Nigerian banks have put mechanisms in place, such as loan restructuring and recovery strategies, to mitigate their adverse impact. The insignificance implies that non-performing loans, while important, do not independently determine bank profitability in the studied context.

Additionally, the loan-to-deposit ratio demonstrates a negative and insignificant effect on performance. This underscores the potential dangers of excessive lending relative to deposits, as it may compromise liquidity and stability if not properly managed. The finding signals that while credit expansion is essential, maintaining a healthy balance between loans and deposits is crucial to prevent financial strain and ensure long-term sustainability.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, one major proposed policy recommendation is that Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should strengthen prudential regulations relating to bank lending practices and credit risk management to ensure that deposit money banks maintain healthy loan portfolios and minimize the incidence of non-performing loans.

Also, the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) should intensify its supervisory and monitoring role to ensure early detection of deteriorating loan quality among deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Deposit Money Banks should also adopt advanced credit risk assessment techniques such as data-driven credit scoring systems and enhanced borrower screening procedures to reduce the likelihood of loan defaults.

The Federal Ministry of Finance and monetary authorities should implement policies that encourage balanced credit expansion while keeping financial stability in the banking sector.

Finally, Banks should improve deposit mobilization strategies and diversify their funding sources to keep a sustainable loan-to-deposit ratio and reduce liquidity risks.

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